

This README file was generated on 2023-11-30 by Samara Brandsen & Louise Vermorcken.

1. Title of Dataset: Reactive response to predation risk affects foraging time of hares, yet not their phosphorus intake

2. Author Information

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3. Date of data collection (single date, range, approximate date): 2014-2015

4. Geographic location of data collection: in a coastal dune landscape (52°33'N, 4°38'E) in the Netherlands

5. Information about funding sources that supported the collection of the data: Funding Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO), 023.001.222, Martijn Weterings.

SHARING/ACCESS INFORMATION

1. Licenses/restrictions placed on the data: None

2. Links to publications that cite or use the data:

Brandsen, S., Vermorcken, L.S., Kuipers, H.J., van Wieren, S.E., de Jonge, I.K. & Weterings, M.J.A. (2023). Reactive response to predation risk affects foraging time of hares, yet not their phosphorus intake. *Mammalian Biology* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42991-023-00385-0>

3. Links to other publicly accessible locations of the data: None

4. Links/relationships to ancillary data sets: None

5. Was data derived from another source? Partially (see A)
A. If yes, list source(s): Weather data (temperature and rainfall) was obtained from the weather station IJmuiden (approximately 10 km from Castricum) (Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut 2020).

Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut. (2020). Klimatologie: daggegevens van het weer in Nederland. Retrieved on June 15 2020, from <http://projects.knmi.nl/klimatologie/daggegevens/selectie.cgi>

6. Recommended citation for this dataset:

Brandsen, S., Vermorcken, L.S., Kuipers, H.J., van Wieren, S.E., de Jonge, I.K. & Weterings, M.J.A. (2023). Data from: Reactive response to predation risk affects foraging time of hares, yet not their phosphorus intake. Dryad Digital Repository. <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.05qfttf95>

DATA & FILE OVERVIEW

1. File List:

- A) DATASET HAAS GOED.csv
- B) MODEL2_Hare_model2Final.sav
- C) MODEL3_Feeding_model_zonderHEIGHT.sav
- D) MODEL4_SPSS_IntakePNIEUW.sav

2. Relationship between files, if important: File B, C and D are derived from file A.

3. Additional related data collected that was not included in the current data package: None

4. Are there multiple versions of the dataset? No
A. If yes, name of file(s) that was updated: NA
i. Why was the file updated? NA
ii. When was the file updated? NA

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DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: DATASET HAAS GOED.csv

1. Number of variables: 12

2. Number of cases/rows: 1391

3. Variable List:

- * Hare.ID = Hare identification
- * Sex = Sex of hare
- * Bodyweight = Bodyweight of hare (numeric)
- * Treatment_dayblockID = Number of treatment day
- * Temp = Average temperature in degrees Celsius (numeric)
- * Average_Windspeed.0.1m = Average windspeed in m/h (numeric)
- * Treatment = Sound (Hare, Sheep, and Control)
- * Prior_treatment = Treatment what was given prior to the new treatment
- * Hour_start_sound = Hour since the start of the sound
- * Average_height = Average vegetation height in centimeters (numeric)
- * Fac_Costly_Vigilance = Amount of time sitting alert plus time sitting (factor)
- * Total_Rainfall.0.1mm = Rainfall

4. Missing data codes: None

5. Specialized formats or other abbreviations used: None

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DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: MODEL2_Hare_model2Final.sav

1. Number of variables: 11

2. Number of cases/rows: 1227

3. Variable List:

- * HareID = Hare identification
- * Sex = Sex of hare
- * Bodyweight = Bodyweight of hare (numeric)
- * Treatment_dayblockID = Number of treatment day
- * Temp = Average temperature in degrees Celsius(numeric)
- * Average_Windspeed01m = Average windspeed in m/h (numeric)
- * Treatment = Sound (Hare, Sheep, and Control)
- * Prior_treatment = Treatment what was given prior to the new treatment
- * Hour_start_sound = Hour since the start of the sound
- * Rainfall_class = Rainfall (presence/absence)
- * Average_height = Average vegetation height in centimeters

4. Missing data codes: None

5. Specialized formats or other abbreviations used: None

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DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: MODEL3_Feeding_model_zonderHEIGHT.sav

1. Number of variables: 12

2. Number of cases/rows: 1342

3. Variable List:

- * HareID = Hare identification
- * Sex = Sex of hare
- * Bodyweight = Bodyweight of hare (numeric)
- * Treatment_dayblockID = Number of treatment day
- * Date = Date of treatment
- * Temp = Average temperature in degrees Celsius(numeric)
- * Average_Windspeed01m = Average windspeed in m/h (numeric)
- * Treatment = Sound (Hare, Sheep, and Control)
- * Hour_start_sound = Hour since the start of the sound
- * Fac_Feeding = Amount of time foraging in minutes
- * Timeofday = Time of day (factor)
- * RainClass = Rainfall (presence/absence)

4. Missing data codes: None

5. Specialized formats or other abbreviations used: None

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DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: MODEL4_SPSS_IntakePNIEUW.sav

1. Number of variables: 11

2. Number of cases/rows: 1342

3. Variable List:

- * HareID = Hare identification
- * Sex = Sex of hare
- * Bodyweight = Bodyweight of hare (numeric)
- * Treatment_dayblockID = Number of treatment day
- * Temp = Average temperature in degrees Celsius(numeric)
- * Average_Windspeed01m = Average windspeed in m/h (numeric)
- * Treatment = Sound (Hare, Sheep, and Control)
- * Prior_treatment = Treatment what was given prior to the new treatment
- * Hour_start_sound = Hour since the start of the sound
- * log_Foodintake10000 = Phosphorous intake
- * RainClass = Rainfall (presence/absence)

4. Missing data codes: None

5. Specialized formats or other abbreviations used: None